

Exposure	Outcome	SNP	Beta	SE	P
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Acute myeloid leukemia	IVW(fixed effects)	0.6731047	0.5231267	0.1982005
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Acute myeloid leukemia	IVW(fixed effects)	0.6731047	0.5231267	0.1982005
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Anal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-2.694463	0.8930083	0.0025505
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Anal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-2.694463	0.8930083	0.0025505
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Basal cell carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.387116	0.1424165	0.0065639
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Basal cell carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.387116	0.1424165	0.0065639
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Bladder cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.0017822	7.71E-04	0.0208282
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Bladder cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.0017822	7.71E-04	0.0208282
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Breast cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.2779708	0.0408176	9.76E-12
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Breast cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.2779708	0.0408176	9.76E-12
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Bronchial cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.681096	0.2015083	7.25E-04
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Bronchial cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.681096	0.2015083	7.25E-04
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Cervical cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.45224	0.130944	5.53E-04
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Cervical cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.45224	0.130944	5.53E-04
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Cervix uteri cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.2778914	0.4789211	0.5617497
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Cervix uteri cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.2778914	0.4789211	0.5617497
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.497785	0.2608813	0.0563795
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.497785	0.2608813	0.0563795
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Chronic lymphocytic leukemia	IVW(fixed effects)	0.3255442	0.4899268	0.5063862
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Chronic lymphocytic leukemia	IVW(fixed effects)	0.3255442	0.4899268	0.5063862
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Chronic myelogenous leukemia	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.234008	0.8812251	0.161414
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Chronic myelogenous leukemia	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.234008	0.8812251	0.161414
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Coloc cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.0023599	8.14E-04	0.0037545
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Coloc cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.0023599	8.14E-04	0.0037545
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Connective tissue cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.068109	0.5172911	0.8952497
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Connective tissue cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.068109	0.5172911	0.8952497
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Endometrial cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.147494	0.0992201	0.137139
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Endometrial cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.147494	0.0992201	0.137139
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Esophageal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.153735	0.1779933	0.3877446
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Esophageal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.153735	0.1779933	0.3877446

KCNJ11+ABCC8	Eye cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.9768852	0.6825618	0.1523718
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Eye cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.9768852	0.6825618	0.1523718
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Gastric cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.409798	0.1010321	4.99E-05
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Gastric cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.409798	0.1010321	4.99E-05
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.7608413	0.6298389	0.2270498
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.7608413	0.6298389	0.2270498
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Kidney cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.0642569	0.2554542	0.8013969
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Kidney cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.0642569	0.2554542	0.8013969
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Laryngeal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.528686	0.5638388	0.3484217
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Laryngeal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.528686	0.5638388	0.3484217
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Liver cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.1469196	0.4572811	0.747991
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Liver cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.1469196	0.4572811	0.747991
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Lung adenocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.0526165	0.1055953	0.6182831
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Lung adenocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.0526165	0.1055953	0.6182831
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Melanoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.001477	7.56E-04	0.0507759
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Melanoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.001477	7.56E-04	0.0507759
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Multiple myeloma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.970295	0.418459	0.0204095
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Multiple myeloma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.970295	0.418459	0.0204095
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Non hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.2269477	0.247945	0.3600264
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Non hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.2269477	0.247945	0.3600264
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Oral cavity cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.000295	0.3567921	0.0050539
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Oral cavity cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.000295	0.3567921	0.0050539
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.299896	0.265631	0.2588996
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.299896	0.265631	0.2588996
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Ovarian carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.3568564	0.0864404	3.65E-05
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Ovarian carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.3568564	0.0864404	3.65E-05
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Pancreas cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.3886212	0.3625443	1.28E-04
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Pancreas cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.3886212	0.3625443	1.28E-04
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.449164	0.3663356	7.63E-05
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.449164	0.3663356	7.63E-05
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Pleural mesothelioma	IVW(fixed effects)	1.489059	0.6380653	0.019611

KCNJ11+ABCC8	Pleural mesothelioma	IVW(fixed effects)	1.489059	0.6380653	0.019611
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Prostate cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.2809691	0.1083885	0.0095353
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Prostate cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.2809691	0.1083885	0.0095353
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Rectal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.048038	0.2414027	0.842268
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Rectal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.048038	0.2414027	0.842268
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Salivary gland carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	1.4718816	0.9007193	0.1022341
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Salivary gland carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	1.4718816	0.9007193	0.1022341
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Small cell lung carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.237895	0.1998698	0.233949
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Small cell lung carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.237895	0.1998698	0.233949
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Small intestine cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.5136527	0.7043831	0.0316419
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Small intestine cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.5136527	0.7043831	0.0316419
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Squamous cell carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.253184	0.3916351	0.5179685
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Squamous cell carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.253184	0.3916351	0.5179685
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.4596833	0.2101293	0.0286972
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.4596833	0.2101293	0.0286972
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Testicular cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.3878842	0.3279624	0.2369244
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Testicular cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.3878842	0.3279624	0.2369244
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Thyroid cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.0725205	0.3396402	0.8309203
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Thyroid cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.0725205	0.3396402	0.8309203
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Tongue cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.133134	0.514902	0.0277588
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Tongue cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.133134	0.514902	0.0277588
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Vulvar cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.155957	0.8683207	0.857461
KCNJ11+ABCC8	Vulvar cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.155957	0.8683207	0.857461